

THE USE OF THE DRUG PERGLIM IN THE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS IN PATIENTS

Narmetova Sevara Yangiboevna

Assistant of Samarkand State Medical University

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Type 2 diabetes mellitus is a disease associated with a violation of the exchange of methods of disease. This type of disease develops for reasons. Some of the disease has a genetic origin, heads lifestyle, stress or garden with environmental factors. Diabetes was the direct cause of 1.5 million deaths worldwide in 2019. In addition, in almost half of wives, the disease was fatal in people aged 60-70 years. The basis of death is a garden with information about the disease (nephropathy, neuropathy, retinopathy, diabetic game, etc.)

With Type 2 diabetes, most young people, obese, over 40 young people are minority limited. Type 2 diabetes mellitus it is insulin-free diabetes says. Reason: lack of sensitivity of B-cells to insulin. Tip 2 the main difference between diabetes mellitus is the immunity of body cells against the definition of the hormone insulin, i.e. their insulin resistance. In a healthy person, insulin provides an "order" for the type to "enter" glucose, which is the main source of energy into the cell membranes. In patients with Type 2 diabetes, the cell does not perceive the "orders" of insulin and the membrane becomes "locked". Type 2 diabetes is much more common than Type 1 diabetes and is diagnosed in 90 foyizas of people with high quality sugar (hyperglycemia). If earlier the disease developed after the age of 40, today Type 2 diabetes occurs in much younger people, the number of patients is growing every year. The complication of not being treated in time is the cause of disability.

In the treatment of what kind of diabetes-peroral is used hypoglycemic drug perglim tablet (reference to the group of sulfonylmochevina of the III generation). It can work for Type II diabetes. Parchment base stimulates the release of insulin from pancreatic B cells orcali works. As with other sulfonylmochevina preparations, this definition is the inclusion of pancreatic cells in physiologicclucose stimulation, the perglim tablet turns out 2mg, 4mg. ASOS 2 Type enteral is used in the treatment of diabetes with these remedies, together with the remedies biguanides (metformin, siophore, diaformin) are added. These tools have helped increase cell sensitivity. Pergym sulfonylmochevina preparations absorb the secretion of insulin by closing the garden potassium channel to the ATP, which is located in the membrane of the pancreas B cell. The closure of the potassium channel leads to depolarization of the B-cell and the opening of calcium channels leads to an increase in the flow of calcium into the cell, which in turn leads to the release of insulin behind exotositosis.

High efficacy was achieved when Perglim was used in single-dose patients. Perglim is given 30 minutes before meals. In patients with diabetes mellitus, manual 24-hour duration of preparation 1 time per day'ri metabolic control was provided.

When we called the parchment (where 13mm / mol was) 2mg in the morning, where was 8mm/mol on the 4th day in a patient given before meals.

The patient was given perglim 2mg on the lower abdomen for 1 month, the sugar content fell to 7mm/Mol. Assigned to the patient for strict admission.

The tests carried out showed that parchment was found to attract attention on the hand in the treatment of Type 2 diabetes mellitus and allowed the same grip.

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